

APPLICATION OF THE DRUG "TRAUMEL WITH" U SICK WITH PURULENT- INFLAMMATORY DISEASES MAXILLOFACIAL AREA

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ABSTRACT

Patients with purulent-inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial area make up about 15-20 % of patients visiting dental clinics and more than 60% of patients receiving medical care in maxillofacial surgery departments . In patients hospitalized in departments with a diagnosis of abscess or phlegmon , there are from 35% to 70% of the total number of patients. According to various authors, from 30% to 40% of dental beds are for patients diagnosed with odontogenic osteomyelitis..

Introduction: Diseases of the maxillofacial region are one of the main signs of a severe course of the disease, complications of which can be acute odontogenic mediastinitis, meningitis, sepsis, thrombosis of the dural sinuses. As a result, the number of deaths increases, which, according to various authors, range from 25% to 55%, especially with the generalization of the inflammatory process leading to septic shock, where the number of deaths increases to 80% [1,3,4]. The problem of inflammatory diseases of the tissues of the maxillofacial region and neck deserves special attention and this is explained by the significant number of patients with inflammatory diseases and the steady growth of progressive phlegmons, spreading to several cellular spaces. The main factor in the occurrence of purulent-inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial area is chronic stress, nutritional errors, alcoholism, drug addiction, which leads to changes in the nonspecific and immunological reactivity of the body.

Treatment of patients with purulent-inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial area is increasing day by day and does not lose its relevance, which requires an integrated approach, surgical and conservative treatment methods aimed at combating microorganisms of coccal origin, general intoxication of the body, and stimulating regeneration processes. In recent years, much attention in the specialized literature has been paid to the use of drugs that limit the impact of adverse factors on the body. Such factors include purulent inflammation and associated intoxication [4,5,6,7,8,9]. One of these drugs is the peptide Deltaran , synthesized by domestic scientists , which has an analgesic, detoxifying , and adaptive effect. However, in the

literature available to us, we have not found information about the use of the drug Traumeel S in acute purulent-inflammatory processes.

Objective: To evaluate the increased effectiveness of complex treatment of patients with purulent-inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial area using the drug " Trumeel S".

Materials and methods of research: To solve the assigned problems, we carried out research in two stages. At the first stage, the pharmacoepidemiology of drugs used in the treatment of patients with acute purulent inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial area was assessed. At the second stage of the work, the structure and resistance profile of pathogens isolated from patients with purulent inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial area were studied. The work summarizes materials from the diagnosis and treatment of 44 patients with phlegmons and abscesses of the maxillofacial region of various localization and prevalence, aged from 15 to 78 years. It should be noted that when using the terms "phlegmon of the maxillofacial region" and "phlegmon of the face," we mean phlegmon of odontogenic etiology.

- medical history
- patient registration cards (RFCs) (these cards included passport data (full name, gender, age, medical history number), date of admission and discharge, diagnosis (main, concomitant, complication of the main),
- information about the ongoing ABT (drugs, doses, frequency, duration, route of drug administration, change of antibiotics during treatment)
- treatment outcomes (improvement, recovery, no effect)
- Acceptable samples for bacteriological examination

- puncture of the cavity of the inflammatory process, separated from the fistula tracts;
- rinsing with water during dialysis of the maxillary sinus;
- sequestrectomy ;
- bacteriological research;
- Statistical processing of results;
- surgical opening of the inflammatory focus

Research results:

Structure of the maxillofacial surgical site in the maxillofacial surgery hospital

Conclusion: We studied the features of the use of the drug " Traumeel S" on the clinical course of 44 patients with purulent-inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial area, in whom complex treatment was carried out using the traditional method; and patients with recommended complex treatment, as part of complex therapy, received daily local injections around the inflammatory focus with the drug Traumeel S.

Traumeel S. was assessed according to clinical and cytological data in patients with acute purulent odontogenic periostitis of the jaws and boils and carbuncles of the maxillofacial area of postoperative wounds, which helped to reduce their contamination, the intensity was significantly reduced.

Positive clinical and laboratory indicators according to microbiological and cytological studies contributed to a reduction in the length of hospitalization

An algorithm has been developed for the use of the drug Traumeel S. in the treatment of patients with purulent-inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial area.

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